

IMPORTANCE OF ORGANIC FARMING, PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPMENT AND TODAY'S PLACE OF PRODUCTION OF ECOLOGICALLY CLEAN PRODUCTS ACCORDING TO WORLD STANDARDS

G'oziyev Umrzoq Lapasovich

G'oibova Sevara Ayup qizi

Imomnazarov Odiljon

Gulistan State University

Abstract: With the increase in population growth, the need for food is increasing day by day. This requires the cultivation of high-quality food products, intensive planting of plants with rational use of land, and high yield, as well as paying special attention to its ecological quality. This article discusses the importance and relevance of organic agriculture today.

Keywords: "Organic" agriculture, environmentally friendly product, GMO, chemicals, pesticide, herbicide, genetically modified, ecological environment.

Introduction. Today, the production of products that are safe for human health has become one of the urgent issues. As a result of the consumption of various synthetic products or genetically modified (GMO) fruits and vegetables, various genetic and chromosomal diseases began to appear among the population. Since the 1960s, the use of chemicals such as fertilizers and pesticides has increased significantly. Constant use of pesticides has led to diseases like cancer, epilepsy and people have suffered for years. This is one of the issues that concern not only us Uzbek people, but also the peoples of the whole world. In such conditions, the concept of "ORGANIC PRODUCT" appeared.

Main Part : Organic agriculture is growing rapidly and today at least 141 countries are growing organic food. Organic food is grown on approximately 32.2 million hectares worldwide and managed by more than 1.2 million producers and farmers. About 65 percent of the countries practicing organic farming are developing countries. The largest areas of organically managed agricultural land area: Oceania, Europe and Latin America. Australia, Argentina and Brazil are the countries with the largest organically managed land areas.

the health of the nation depends on the nutrition of the people and the standards of quality and safety indicators of the products consumed, attention is paid at the level of public policy to ensure the healthy nutrition of the population. In our country, this area is regulated within the framework of the Law "On Organic Products" adopted in April of this year.

According to the order of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 126-F of February 13, 2017 and the order of the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Management No. 122 of

April 24, 2017, on August 22-23, 2017 in the city of Tashkent and on August 24 in the city of Samarkand " "Scientific and Institutional Basis of Development of Organic Agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Central Asia" was held an international conference to deliver high-quality, ecologically clean, competitive agricultural products to the world market under the "Uzbekbrand" was dedicated.

Effect of mineral fertilizers

was very fertile, rich in various minerals and fertilizers. Recently, finding lands rich in natural minerals is a problematic issue. The richest and most saturated soils are located near volcanoes and under the sea.

When mineral fertilizers are applied in excess of the norm for the purpose of enriching the soil, their main part is absorbed by plants, and the remaining part accumulates in the soil in a form that cannot be absorbed by crops. It passes into the form of nitrate and phosphate salts. They gradually dissolve under the influence of water, reach the deep layers of the earth (up to 12 m) with water, join the seepage waters and pollute them. Phosphorous fertilizers not only accumulate as phosphate salts, but also lead to the accumulation of heavy metals.

As a result of excessive use of chemicals over the years, the soil becomes saturated with toxic substances, which spread from the soil through the roots of the plant to all organs, and the plant's crop contains more than the prescribed amount. These toxic chemicals have negative effects on plants and all other living organisms.

Therefore, the use of various chemicals is prohibited in organic farming. Instead, clean, natural fertilizers (manure, straw, composts, siderate crops and other organic products) are used.

Water requirements for growing organic products

In Uzbekistan, water pollution index (SII) is used for comprehensive assessment of water quality. According to the classification adopted in our republic, surface water bodies are divided into 7 categories:

- very clean (SII-0.3 and less);
- clean (SII-0.31-1.0);
- moderately clean (SII-1.1-2.5);
- polluted (SII-2.51-4.0);
- dirty (SII-4.1-6.0);
- very dirty (SII-6.1-10.0);
- too dirty (more than SII-10.0).

In the cultivation of organic agricultural products, it is recommended to use water of 1-3 categories.

Organic in the sustainable development of the republic's agriculture contribution of agriculture:

- from an economic point of view: official guarantee of organic agricultural products grown in the Republic and growth of the market of organic products in the world;

- facilitating access of agricultural producers to foreign markets and expanding export geography;

- increasing the economic efficiency of production due to the sale of developed products at relatively high prices;

- from a social point of view: - to care about the health of the future generation and to strengthen a healthy lifestyle in order to raise a mature generation;

- to improve the quality of agricultural products in terms of naturalness, taste and usefulness;

- ecologically: reduction of negative effects on the environment and prevention of degradation of soil fertility;

-maintain biological diversity, ecological stability and equality of the ecosystem

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can say that in the production of organic products, factors such as climate, soil, topography and water supply are taken into account. Depending on the ecological conditions, the cultivation of fresh produce is carried out in irrigated, dry, seepage waters close to the surface of the earth, saline, erosion-prone lands. Controversy over profitability and productivity gains in organic farming is fierce, but there is a strong preference for its environmentally friendly nature and ability to protect human health. Many studies have shown that organic agriculture is efficient and sustainable. It not only improves our current life, but also contributes to the creation of an acceptable way of life for future generations.

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